

DEVELOPING KEY COMPETENCIES THROUGH THE INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH

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Abstract. *The article discusses the cognitive activities, skills and competencies common to different academic disciplines, and their application methods for developing interdisciplinary competencies. One of the main problems of today is to develop in-depth knowledge, skills, competencies and competence-based approaches in the chosen profession of graduates of educational institutions. Interdisciplinary integration increases students' interest in their profession and science, strengthens their knowledge, and provides a basis for the formation of practical skills, competencies and competences.*

Keywords: *competency, interdisciplinary, skill, competence, approach, integration, competence.*

Introduction

In order to develop interdisciplinary competencies, it is necessary to identify and highlight the common cognitive activities, skills, abilities, and methods of application shared across different subjects. One of the main issues today is that graduates of educational institutions must develop deep knowledge, skills, abilities, and competencies related to their chosen profession through a competency-based approach.

Interdisciplinary integration increases students' interest in their profession and subject areas, strengthens their knowledge, and helps them develop practical skills, abilities, and competencies.

This process can be organized, as shown in Table 10, on the basis of interdisciplinary connections in three directions: general education subjects, general professional subjects, and specialized subjects. The integration of general education subjects (such as physics) with general professional subjects is carried out together with specialized subjects.

One of today's main challenges is ensuring that graduates develop deep knowledge, skills, abilities, and a competency-based approach in their chosen field. Interdisciplinary integration increases students' interest in their profession and subjects, reinforces their knowledge, and shapes their practical skills, abilities, and competencies.

To address the challenges of implementing interdisciplinary integration, it is necessary to improve the methods of teaching physics by solving the following issues:

- Using tools that enable the integration of mathematics and professional subjects;
- Ensuring and motivating the three-way integration of the educational process;
- Improving the goals, content, methods, types, and tools of education.

The educational content of the subjects can be divided into the following structural areas:

1. The field of mathematics education a scope of knowledge that develops students' scientific worldview and philosophical thinking skills;
2. The field of general professional education a scope of knowledge that shapes theoretical knowledge related to future technical professions;

3. The field of specialized education an area that develops professional training.

These three areas are limited in scope and consist of a set of knowledge, skills, and competencies specific to a given subject. If studied separately, this knowledge remains fragmented and does not explain the connections between phenomena.

Diagram of interdisciplinary connections Table 2.4

4th Area: The content of education based on the integration of mathematics and general professional subjects (OB) is a scope of knowledge that develops students’ scientific worldview and philosophical reasoning abilities, while also forming their understanding of theoretical knowledge related to their profession through the laws and phenomena of mathematics [3.8.].

5th Area: The content of education based on the integration of mathematics and specialized subjects (OB) is a scope of knowledge that shapes students’ understanding of the interrelation between natural phenomena and the practical knowledge relevant to their professional training.

6th Area: The content of education based on the integration of general professional and specialized subjects (OB) is a scope of knowledge that shapes students’ theoretical and practical professional knowledge, skills, and abilities.

These areas (4–6) are considered “continuous areas” and consist of a set of knowledge that partially ensures the implementation of interdisciplinary integration (FAB). However, students’ knowledge in these areas is relatively generalized and does not always enable them to fully explain the connections between phenomena.

7th Area: The content of education based on the integration of physics, general professional, and specialized subjects (OB) is a scope of knowledge that shapes students’ mathematical and professional knowledge, practical skills, and abilities in a harmonized manner. This area is called the “harmonized area” and consists of a set of knowledge that ensures exemplary implementation of interdisciplinary integration (FAB). In this case, students’ knowledge is generalized enough to consistently explain the connections between phenomena on a scientific basis and to interpret real-life situations they encounter by relying on fundamental knowledge.

Therefore, the scope of knowledge described in the 7th area should be reflected in the education of 11th-grade general secondary school students. This will significantly influence the quality and effectiveness of education.

The implementation of interdisciplinary integration (OB) of mathematics and specialized subjects for students can be organized in four stages:

1. Studying the issues of OB between mathematics and specialized subjects and the underlying principles (teachers’ theoretical preparation);
2. Differentiating knowledge based on FAB principles (preparation for specific lessons);

3. Integrating the knowledge to be studied according to relevant topics, based on FAB principles;
4. Organizing the lesson based on FAB. [9.]

The first stage includes teachers' independent activities related to the educational process. In the second stage, the essence of FAB is studied deeply, and the knowledge to be mastered is clearly identified. In the third stage, this knowledge is integrated from the perspective of the OB requirements for mathematics and specialized subjects. In the fourth stage, this knowledge is directly applied in practice, that is, delivered to students during the lesson.

Through problem-solving in the learning process, various educational, upbringing, and developmental tasks are accomplished. In the learning process, students learn the content of the topic and how to solve problems through solving interdisciplinary problems. Solving problems holds a special place in improving the effectiveness of education, helping students achieve their learning goals, acquiring full knowledge, and developing key competencies. Therefore, organizing more problem-solving activities in lessons and developing methods for using them is put forward as one of the pressing issues in developing teaching methodology based on interdisciplinary integration. [2,3]

In the process of solving problems based on interdisciplinary connections, students gain an understanding of the new knowledge content needed by society by applying interdisciplinary links, become familiar with new situations presented in the problem conditions, and discover new methods for themselves by applying laws and theories from various subjects to solve the given problem. By repeatedly solving problems of a certain type through interdisciplinary connections, students not only develop skills and abilities but also expand their knowledge based on interdisciplinary integration.

Solving problems based on integrative knowledge enables students to distinguish precise ideas, draw conclusions, identify information and scientific facts, match and compare information, and recognize contradictions.

Research has shown that many teachers struggle to solve problems using an interdisciplinary approach; the main reason is their inability to apply interdisciplinary connections in the problem-solving process. In the teaching process, interdisciplinary connections play a key role, since explaining any phenomenon scientifically requires a multifaceted approach.

One of the important didactic requirements of problem-solving is that, during the implementation of interdisciplinary connections, the teacher should select the most convenient ways to present the problem to the student. In fulfilling these tasks, the teacher must consistently organize the solution of interdisciplinary problems both in class and through extracurricular activities, moving from simple to complex tasks. The teacher must organize this process in a way that theory and practice of interdisciplinary connections are effectively combined. By doing so, the teacher not only improves their own professional competence but also lays the foundation for students to develop basic and subject-specific competencies through solving interdisciplinary problems. [4,5,6.]

Opportunities to develop interdisciplinary competencies when studying certain topics have been identified. One of the important forms of connection in physics is solving mathematical problems using physical laws. Solving problems that relate simultaneously to both physics and mathematics is beneficial for students. The subject of physics is connected not only with arithmetic or algebraic expressions but also with geometry. Certain topics also offer opportunities for developing interdisciplinary competencies.

Currently, modern socio-economic and political relations in the world require the use of innovative technologies in the educational process across all subjects. This, in turn, helps ensure the quality of education, develop students' creative abilities, increase the effectiveness of the practical application of subjects, and guide students toward their future professions based on interdisciplinary connections. Wide-ranging research is being conducted on these issues.

Developing the thinking of 10th- and 11th-grade students based on interdisciplinary connections is of great importance because they study natural phenomena through academic subjects. The world is unified, and the things and phenomena that make it up are closely interconnected. Therefore, the subjects that study natural phenomena must also be taught in an interconnected manner.

General cultural competencies, learning and cognitive, informational, communicative, and socio-labor competencies are all relevant here. In our research, we divided key competencies into the following categories:

1. Communicative;
2. Working with information;
3. Self-development as an individual;
4. Active civic engagement;
5. General cultural;
6. Mathematical literacy and awareness of scientific and technological innovations;
7. Mathematical thinking;
8. Working with graphs;
9. Working with formulas;
10. Justifying results. [5]

The stages of learning general education subjects in the education system and the related basic and subject-specific competencies are presented accordingly.

1–4. Core and Subject-Specific General Competencies

Currently, in our country’s education system, based on experimental results and research, core subject-specific competencies have been developed for students in grades 10–11.

Communicative competence (A2, A2+):

The student should have an understanding of the subject, be able to use basic concepts both in their native language and in at least one foreign language. They should be able to respond to the teacher’s questions and complete recommended learning tasks related to the topic, and engage in communication at school, in the community, in public places, at home, and with classmates while observing moral and ethical norms.

Information literacy competence (A1, A2+):

A 10–11th grade student should be able to find information about the latest developments and progress in the subject within the country using popular scientific materials; create an outline for the topic studied based on instructions given in the textbook introduction; find answers to questions using the text; complete practical assignments; sort, process, store, and effectively use information found in media sources; create tables, diagrams, and graphs; find definitions and rules; and use media tools to search for information and materials about the subject.

Self-development competence (A2, A2+):

Actively participate in lessons, extracurricular and out-of-class activities; monitor their own behavior in nature; develop themselves spiritually, mentally, and intellectually; and continuously study and improve their knowledge and experience independently throughout life.

Socially active citizenship competence (A2, A2+):

The student should understand the scientific and practical importance of the subject and its relevance to humans and nature; observe and conduct experiments on the phenomena and processes studied by the subject; and, recognizing their role in society, feel responsible for natural events and processes.

National and general cultural competence (A2, A2+):

Show compassion, generosity, and respect for others’ worldviews; observe cultural norms and lead a healthy lifestyle.

Mathematical literacy and awareness of scientific and technological innovations (A2, A2+):

Independently solve subject-related problems and exercises; complete standard tasks; read and use various formulas, models, drawings, graphs, and diagrams throughout life.

In accordance with the principles of continuity and coherence of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and based on the priority of students’ individual interests and age characteristics, the following core competencies are formed:

Table 1.1

Stages of studying the subject in general secondary education schools

Stage of Education	Graduates	Standard Level	Level Name
	Graduates of general secondary schools, grades 10–11	A2	Basic level of subject study

General secondary education	Graduates of grades 10–11 of general secondary schools with advanced subject study and specialized schools	A2+	Enhanced basic level of subject study
	Graduates of grades 10–11 of general secondary schools	A2	Core level of subject study

Once the technology for designing core and subject-specific competencies has been developed, the principles for selecting appropriate teaching methods naturally follow from this approach.

In grades 10–11, topics that repeated content from earlier stages were removed; attention was given to an interdisciplinary integrative approach; [1,2,3] and topics were revised based on the principle of developing students’ life skills while considering their age and psycho-physiological development. We also introduced new competencies such as mathematical reasoning, justifying results, working with graphs, and working with formulas.

The authors emphasized that, in order to successfully implement this in the education system, the following points are of critical importance for all levels of the pedagogical system:

- **Changing the structure and content of education:** shifting from isolated theoretical concepts accumulated across separate subjects to methods that provide a universal understanding of the world and can be applied through practical and social skills;
- **Changing the approach to educational goals and outcomes:** moving from students passively absorbing information to embedding it in their social and intellectual culture, thereby qualitatively shaping their worldview;
- **Transforming the structure of teachers’ pedagogical activities:** shifting from one-way delivery of material to engaging in dialogue with students and fostering their personal development;
- **Introducing a competency-based approach into the general secondary education environment;** incorporating changes related to mass media, social reality, family, the country, culture, others;
- **Reforming technological support:**
- **Transitioning to innovative technologies and software aimed at developing students’ activities;** strengthening the system’s organizational, human resources, material-technical, and financial support [6,7,18].

Given that our country is pursuing innovative development, it has all the necessary conditions to move to a modern educational model. Building this model requires the effective use of scientific and technical potential and deep reliance on the achievements of both fundamental and applied sciences. Implementing these technologies in practice is based on increasing the number of highly qualified, talented national specialists.

Conclusion. In a system of continuous education, a priority task is to prepare competent specialists who can assert themselves in real life, actively contribute to transforming society, and influence it positively. There are still a number of issues that need to be addressed to practically implement state educational standards (SES) and curricula based on a competency-based approach [8].

For example:

- By what methods and teaching technologies can students' competencies be effectively formed and developed?
- Are students ready for this?
- Do current textbooks, virtual labs, and practical lesson materials really support the development of students' competencies?

From this perspective, the education system must develop and implement the scientific-methodological, psychological-pedagogical foundations, as well as the didactic and methodological tools and methods necessary for a competency-based approach in practice.

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